

Integration Of Rom And Egyptian Students In The Albanian School, In The Context Of Inclusion - Exploratory Study - Çajupi School, Albania-

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 16, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 18, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Integration, Rom and Egyptian community, Action plan, Strategy</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6857128</p>	<p><i>Purpose: The main purpose of this paper is to identify the needs of the school for a comprehensive approach with a clear goal towards social inclusion, aiming to create an action plan for quality integration of the Rom and Egyptian community in the school "A.Z. Çajupi", in accordance with the strategies approved by the Ministry of Education as well as European Union strategies for the inclusion of the Rom and Egyptian communities.</i></p> <p><i>Methods: Participants in this study are 33 students of the school "A.Z. Çajupi"- Tirana, Albania belonging to the Rom and Egyptian community and which include all Rom and Egyptian school students in a population of 1012 students with whom semi-structured interviews and focus group were conducted. The study covers the period April 2021-June 2021.</i></p> <p><i>Results: The obtained data provide us with an overview in figures of problems related to integration and inclusion in school. The achieved conclusions raise the necessity of drafting a strategy/ community action plan for the integration of the Rom and Egyptian community, realized with the necessary participation of this target group, well coordinated with the local development strategy and in line with the strategy and the National Action Plan for the Integration of Rom and Egyptians.</i></p>

Introduction

The distribution of Rom is an issue throughout Europe, but mainly in the Balkans, which represents the cradle of Rom communities in Europe. Albania had a Rom population of 8,301 (0.3%, 2011 official census); however, the current number is thought to be much higher, with other sources putting the total population at 120,000 (Regional Cooperation Council [RCC], 2020).

The livelihood of the Rom community in the Albanian context is characterized by numerous challenges, mainly related to education. School dropout is considered an important issue in Rom community integration. The latest figure for preschool enrollment from 2017 shows that the enrollment of Rom children aged 3 to 5 is only 33% in Albania (RCC, 2020), a worryingly low rate that brings in the perspective of development a language deficit in children, compared to peers attending kindergarten (Cernat, 2019). This language deficit, which is not addressed in time, can create a language barrier between Rom and other groups, contributing to their isolation. Other data suggest that there is a significant difference related to the education of Rom parents. Parents who have several years of schooling are 3 times more likely to enroll their children in school than those who have no schooling years (Cousin et al., 2020). Another reason for not enrolling in school is the early employment of children in begging or trafficking, while according to the Ombudsman, the high dropout rate and irregular attendance is due to the non-creation of a reception environment in schools. (Dauti, 2015).

In 2015, in the Albanian context, one third of Rom children aged 7 to 15 were out of school systems (Meçe, 2015) and given that unofficial estimates put the total number of Rom at around 115,000, it is thought that about 30,000 Rom are of school age in Albania (Dauti, 2015). The high dropout rate, together with irregular attendance and failure to create a school-friendly environment, forces Roma children to move to a Rom-only school, creating a gap between this community and other communities. (Haxhiha, 2013). Currently, in addition to the above reasons that continue to be present, other reasons that may explain the dropout rate of high school students from the Rom community are lack of financial resources and distance from educational facilities (ECRI Report, 2020). In terms of education, Rom girls are particularly disadvantaged, as they have to take on the role of caring for younger siblings, terminating their schooling earlier than Roma boys. Early marriage (girls marry on average between 13 and 15, while boys between 16 and 18 years old) and early motherhood are the main causes of school dropout by girls (Hazizaj et al., 2016).

Subjects and Methods:

Purpose of the paper

The main purpose of this paper is to identify the needs of the school for a comprehensive approach with a clear goal towards social inclusion, aiming to create an action plan for quality integration of the Rom and Egyptian community in the school "A.Z. Çajupi", in accordance with the strategies approved by the Ministry of Education as well as the European Union strategies for the inclusion of the Roma and Egyptian community.

Objectives

1. Identify needs and challenges in relation to the following aspects: school attendance, infrastructure, discrimination and inclusion.
2. Understand the dynamics of the issue of discrimination against the Rom and Egyptian communities, if it is present in the school context, both in relation to teachers and in relation to peers.
3. To analyze the aspects related to the challenges in the school context, which may also reflect the problems in the social and economic context.
4. Develop strategies and action lines that broadly involve the community and that orient in solving the problems that will be identified in this study.

Sample

Gymnasium "A.Z. Çajupi" has 1012 students and 60 teachers of different age groups. In class X there are 369 students of whom 194 are female; in grade XI 335 students of which 176 female and in grade XII 308 students of which 158 female. The contingent of students is heterogeneous, as they come from different 9-year schools which have a significant number of Rom and Egyptian students such as the schools "Bajram Curri" and "Ramazan Jarani." From this population we have selected the sample that includes all students of the Rom and Egyptian community in the school A.Z.Cajupi- Tirana, a total of 33 students.

Some characteristics of the sample:

Students with both parents are (N = 25, or 76%) of children, with one parent (N = 5, or 15%) and without parent (N = 2, or 6%). In both cases where the children do not live with either parent they live with the grandmother who has taken custody of the children; (N = 7, or 28%) of children have both parents at work, (N = 15, or 60%) of children have one parent at work and (N = 3, or 12%) of children have both parents without job; (N = 3, or 60%) of children who live with one of the parents, have an unemployed parent, while (N = 2, or 40%) of children who live with one of the parents have an employed parent.

The selection of students in these classes where the age varies from 15 or 16 years to 19 years is related to the purpose and objectives of the study. The gender distribution of the sample has a slight predominance in favor of boys (N = 21 representing 64% of the total) and (N = 12 were girls, or about 36%). Most of the students (N = 10 belong to the age of 15), (N = 12 students were 16 years old and N = 8 of them 18-19 years old.

Instruments

In order to accurately diagnose the situation, Rom and Egyptian students were interviewed with semi-structured questions, which consisted of providing more detailed information about school attendance, provision of books and school supplies, discrimination in school, integration into classroom activities. The interview was conducted in a climate of interaction oriented more towards a friendly conversation. The process took about 20 minutes, including presentation, study objectives, informed approval, and instruction timing. Students were informed about the study before becoming part of it. Collaboration with the school psychologist and the caretaker teachers helped in the interviews. After the interview, a focus group was conducted, according to grades X, XI, XII to deepen the interview answers.

Procedures

We initially received informed written approval from the parents and the school principal. Students were contacted by psychology and further by us. They were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their data, which would only be used for research purposes. Voluntary student participation was also requested. In the presence of the psychologist the interviews were conducted with semi-structured questions. Communication with the facilitator and psychologist further facilitated the conduct of the interviews. The school principal, the caretaker teacher and the school psychologist helped us with the study. Contact with students was relatively difficult. They were a bit withdrawn and skeptical during the communication process and the conduct of the interview.

After the interview, the focus group was conducted according to the classes in order to deepen the interview answers. These focus groups lasted 45 minutes and the students were actively involved in the discussions.

Results and data analysis:

The data obtained from the analysis of the collected interviews are of interest. They provide us with an overview in figures of issues related to integration and inclusion in the school. The data obtained and processed refer to various aspects that refer to integration. The results of the interview are expressed by categorizing the answers.

Graphic 1. Attendance at school

From the given answers it results that (N = 29, or 88%) of the students have a regular attendance of the school and N = 4, or 12%) of them have an irregular attendance where (N = 2 or 6% are female) and (N = 2, or 6%) are male. Regular attendance of students' responses is also conditioned by the school regulations for pre-university education January 2020 and normative provisions 2013 which clearly define the number of reasonable and unreasonable absences that a student may develop in a school year.

The most relevant answer no.11

"I like school, but I often find it impossible to attend because I have to take care of my grandmother and brothers because I live alone with them."

Graphic 2. Equipping students with books, notebooks and teaching aids

From the given answers it results that (N = 9, or 28%) of the students have very little or no books and tools, (N = 14, or 42% of them have what they consider the most necessary and in a part of are provided by friends and schools and (N = 10, or 30%) have all the tools and books together. As can be seen from the social map of students, the determining factor in the lack of necessary tools is the economic situation of students' families, where some live with only one parent and the rest have unemployed parents.

Graphic 3. Economic situation and equipment with school supplies

As can be seen from the graph, there is a correlation between the economic situation of students and their provision of school supplies. Students without school supplies occupy about 28% of the total where 6% of them are with only one parent at work and 22% of them are without any of the parents at work due to the fact of not having parents or their absence for reasons of divorces, the presence of a parent in prison or their removal. Also 30% of students are with the most necessary tools, of which 3% have unemployed parents.

The most relevant answer number 26:

"I live alone with my mother and she is unemployed, we find it impossible to provide for her to eat and no longer books and notebooks. Teachers and friends with old books have helped me."

Graphic 4. Discrimination in school

From the data analysis we notice that (N = 3, or 9% of students say that they feel discriminated in school, while (N = 20, or 42%) of students think that they sometimes feel discrimination and (N = 16, or 48 %) of students think that they have never felt discrimination.

The most relevant individual answer no. 6:

"I do not feel direct discrimination, but I think there are elements such as the insulting words that are used from time to time, although not directly to me, the word gabel is the most common one that hurts me. Among students there are social groups and learners. they always stick with each other. "

The most relevant individual answer no. 5

"I have never felt discrimination in my address. I feel good because I have a close social circle which helps me a lot."

Graphic 5. Involvement of students in classroom activities

From the data analysis it is noticed that there is an inclusion and non-involvement of students in almost equal activities. Thus (N = 7, or 58%) females and (N = 10, or 48%) males are involved in activities and (N = 5, or 42%) women and (N = 11, or 52%) men are not involved in activities. Below we list the reasons why students are not involved in activities:

- ☒ They think they have no talents
- ☒ They have no desire to participate in activities

Graphic 6. Accompanying during short breaks or long breaks with other students in the class

The results show that there are a large number of students who associate during short breaks or long breaks with other students in the class. Thus (N = 9, or 75% are female) and (N = 15, or 71% are male). The results also show that there are a small number of students who do not socialize with other students in the class during short breaks or long breaks. Thus (N = 3, or 25% are female) and (N = 6, or 29% are male). This group also lists the reasons for not associating with other students:

- ☒ They feel prejudiced by them.
- ☒ They want to associate only with students who belong to the same community.

Graphic 7. Mockery, insults, isolation from other students

To the question: Were there any mockeries, insults or separations from other students (N = 4 or 33%) of girls and (N = 6, or 29%) of male answered that there were mockeries, insults and separations from other students of the class, while (N = 8, or 67%) of women and (N = 15, or 71%) of boys expressed that they did not experience ridicule, insults, isolation from other students.

Graphic 8. Student satisfaction with the way teachers treat them

As can be seen from the graph, all female students, as well as all male students, express that they are satisfied with the way they are treated by teachers at school. No student reports otherwise.

Graphic 9. Differentiations from teachers

Question: Do you notice differences in the behavior of teachers between you and other students in the class?

To this question again all students of these communities (N = 33, or 100%) share the opinion that teachers do not differentiate between students.

Graphic 10. Teacher's attention to other students in the class

To the question: Do teachers pay more attention to other students in the class, all students in these communities (N = 33, or 100%) also answered this question unanimously that teachers do not pay more attention to students other class.

Graphic 11. Teachers' willingness to listen to my ideas

Regarding the readiness of teachers to listen to the ideas of these students, (N = 8, or 67%) women and (N = 14, or 67%) men say that often teachers are willing, while (N = 4, or 33%) of women and (N = 7, or 33%) of men say that very often teachers are willing.

Graphic 12. Problems to follow the development of learning through online platforms

Asked if you had any problems with attending online classes due to electronic devices or internet access, (N = 26, or 80%,) of which (N = 9, or 35%) female and (N = 17, or 65%) men say they have had many difficulties, even inability to attend online learning, as a result of lack of equipment and internet access.

Graphic 13. What do you plan to do after finishing high school?

Asked what they think to do after graduating from high school, (N = 7) of which (N = 4, or 33%) women and (N = 3, or 14%) men say they will continue higher education; (N = 19) of which (N = 6, or 50%) women and (N = 13, or 50%) men say they will work; (N = 7) of whom (N = 2, or 17%) women and (N = 5, or 24%) men say they do not know what to do.

Graphic 14. Obstacles in continuing studies

When asked what prevents you from continuing your studies, (N = 20) of which (N = 7, or 58%) women and (N = 13, or 62%) men say that difficult economic conditions make it impossible to continue of school; (N = 7) of which (N = 3, or 25%) women and (N = 4, or 19%) men say that the family is an obstacle to continuing school, while (N = 6) of which (N = 2, or 17%) of women and (N = 4, or 19%) say that an important factor for not attending school is discrimination by society

Graphic 15. Three things I enjoy about my school

As the graph shows (N = 8) students from these communities, of which (N = 3, or 25%) women and (N = 5, or 24%) men say that they like equal treatment by teachers; (N = 18) of which (N = 6, or 50%) women and (N = 12, or 57%) men say they like the infrastructure and (N = 7) of whom (N = 3, or 25%) women and (N = 4, or 19%) men say that they like the activity organized by the school.

Graphic 16. Three things I do not like about my school

Regarding the things that the students of these communities do not like in school (N = 16), of which (N = 6, or 50%) women and (N = 10, or 48%) men say that they do not like the prejudices of their peers ; (N = 5) of which (N = 2, or 17%) women and (N = 3, or 14%) men say they do not like the location of the school and (N = 12) of whom (N = 4, or 33%) women and (N = 8, or 38%) men say that school lacks practical hours.

Graphic 17. What they seek to improve

When asked what you would like to improve in your school, (N = 13) of students from whom (N = 5, or 42%) women and (N = 8, or 38%) men say that they should develop in school more many sports and artistic activities; (N = 12) of students out of which (N = 4, or 33%) female and (N = 8, or 38%) male say that their opinions should be taken more into account and (N = 8) by which (N = 3, or 25%) women and (N = 5, or 24%) men say that more lessons should be developed in laboratories.

Conclusions:

Based on the purpose of the paper and its objectives we conclude:

Regarding the school attendance by students from these communities referred to the first graph, the results show that 88% of students have regular school attendance and a small percentage, about 12% have irregular school attendance. These results show that school attendance by students from these communities is not a problem and is at a satisfactory level.

Regarding the provision of books and other school supplies, the results show that about 28% of students in these communities have very little or no books and supplies, 42% of them have what they consider most necessary and in some most are provided by friends and schools and 30% have all the tools and books together. What is noticeable is that students in these communities face a lack of books, notebooks and school supplies. Related to this is the difficult economic situation faced by these communities, where part of the students live with only one parent and the rest have unemployed parents.

Referring to the results reflected in Graph 4, 51% of students in these communities suffer from peer prejudice and discrimination, although not directly. The figures show that this discrimination occurs only in the form of ridicule or insults from other students. On the other hand, in no case is the prejudice or discrimination of these students reported by teachers. The results of the study showed that all 33 students of this school belonging to these communities admit that the teachers treat them very well and do not notice any differences that may come from their teachers in relation to other students in the class. They feel supported by their teachers, they even claim that teachers are always interested in these students having regular attendance and also in relation to their progress in school.

The data provided by the study show that the school enables the participation of Roma and Egyptian students in activities, but in terms of participation in them here 51% of students willingly participate in them and 49% do not participate justifying the absence of talent and unwillingness to get involved in activities. They highly value the organization of cultural and sports activities, but they seek to develop more sports and artistic activities in the school, they also seek greater involvement in decision-making in terms of activities.

During the online learning process the quality engagement of Roma students left much to be desired. 80% of students reported having had many problems attending online learning. The inability to attend online learning is related to the difficult conditions that these communities face, the lack of digital equipment, such as: computer, telephone or I-Pad, as well as the inability to access the Internet.

The results of the study showed that only 21% of students belonging to these communities want to continue high school, while 58% of them want to start work. Although these students want to attend university, 60% of them state that the difficult conditions that this community faces are a hindering factor, and 22% claim that the family is another obstacle to continuing school. Also 18% of them claim that another hindering factor is social discrimination.

Students in these communities value equal treatment in school, but they do not like peer prejudice, which leads us to think that they continue to be prejudiced because of color, race, social and economic conditions.

Discussion

Mapping the needs of the Rom community in the Çajupi school. This mapping is very important and serves the school to collect and identify some key indicators to identify and plan the most urgent needs of the Rom and Egyptian community. The school must record the total number of Rom and Egyptian students studying in the 9-year schools that belong to the "Çajupi" gymnasium. An exact number of these students will serve the school to plan social policies.

Drafting a school strategy / action plan for the integration of the Roma and Egyptian community. It is important to have an integrated and strategic approach to the Roma and Egyptian situation and the challenges that come with it.

Building and institutionalizing the partnership between representatives of the school and this community. Specifically, the establishment of an institutionalized multidisciplinary roundtable with the participation of key local actors, which includes: representatives of the Municipality (social services, housing, Office for the Protection of Children's Rights), Region, Prefecture, Local Education Office, Regional Directorate of Health, Regional Employment Office, Police, NGOs dealing with the Roma issue and also representatives of the School Management Staff and representatives of the Roma community.

Creating and facilitating employment opportunities for this community: Cooperation with businesses, Cooperation between the Municipality, the Directorate of Employment and the Regional Directorate of Vocational Training not only to identify jobseekers from this community, but also to inform and provide vocational training courses for interested.

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